

PROJECT RISK MANAGEMENT PRACTICES AND PERFORMANCE OF AFRICAN UNION TRANSITION MISSION PROJECT IN SOMALIA

Gathambiri Peter Nguribu^{1*}, Dr. Elizabeth Nambuswa Makokha (PhD)^{1,2}

¹College of Human Resource Development, Department of Entrepreneurship and Procurement Leadership and Management. Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology, P.O. Box 62000 - 00200, Nairobi Kenya

²College of Human Resource Development, Department of Entrepreneurship and Procurement Leadership and Management. Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology, P.O. Box 62000 - 00200, Nairobi Kenya

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15315256>

Published Date: 30-April-2025

Abstract: The purpose of this study was to determine the effects of project risk management practices on the performance of ATMIS project in Somalia. The study was guided by the following specific objectives; determine effect of risk identification on the performance of ATMIS project in Somalia. The study was guided by the following theories: stakeholders' theory. The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. The target population of this study comprised of 365 from all categories involved in ATMIS, Mogadishu area, which formed the unit of observation of this study. The stratified sampling scientific formula was used to extract the sample size of 131 respondents from the target population, stratified into 3 strata. The study used semi-structured questionnaires as the primary data collection instrument. The data obtained from the survey questions was analyzed using statistical software, Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). To get to know the relationship between independent and dependent variables, the study used descriptive statistics, correlation analysis and regression analysis as tools. The data obtained from focus groups was analyzed using the thematic method. Piloting was done to test the validity and reliability of the data collection instrument. The study concluded that risk identification had a significant effect on performance of the ATMIS project in Somali. The study recommended that the management should conduct a thorough risk identification, for indicators that should be used as techniques in the practice; mind mapping, nominal group technique and brainstorming to avoid trouble in identifying risks due to complexity, and any additional unpredicted event and that the use of a mind mapping approach to managing qualitative data can provide a pragmatic resolution of the tension between limited resources and quality in stakeholders participation processes.

Keywords: Risk Identification, performance of the ATMIS project.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the global setting, successful project risk management techniques are acknowledged as essential to the accomplishment of projects in a number of organizations. Resulting to projects resilient and achieving their objectives. It also helps organizations in predicting and solving issues in advance (Project Management Institute, 2017). Risk identification is one of the practices that helps in pointing out possible risks that might affect the outcome, stakeholders, or the resources of the project. In performing the practice proactively, project teams can innovate ways to alleviate their effects and fortify project resilience (Project Management Institute, 2017). Risks are ranked according to their level of severity through risk assessment practice. The practice allows organizations to be more focused to the risk with the highest effect to the project

and in that are able to allocate more resources (Hillson & Murray-Webster, 2017). Risk mitigation is also a risk management practice that has the following techniques; risk transfer, avoidance tactics, and contingency plans. Effective use of this practice enables organizations to maximize their chances of accomplishing project objectives and reduce interruptions (Heldman & Baca, 2017). The practice of risk monitoring allows project team to beware of risk dynamics and changing risk settings, thereby, guaranteeing quick reaction to new threats. Therefore, risk monitoring system assist to lessen risks impact to the project elements (Kerzner, 2017).

In Africa, efficient risk identification is important, following the unique challenges and uncertainties that are particular to it. Elements including political unpredictability, economic fluctuations, and lack of infrastructure create a complex risk environment. Possible risks and vulnerabilities in organizations are foreseen with the help of vibrant risk identification practice, which opens up the way for proactive risk management processes (Clarke, 2017). According to Munene (2016), companies can strategically allocate resources to manage risks and prioritize them by doing thorough risk assessments. Other examples are culture regulations and socioeconomic situations that help to have an impact on the degree of risk. Organizations in the African region can improve project outcomes and reduce the impact of identified risks by putting in place context-specific risk mitigation strategies (Vogel, 2019). Some of them are investing in capacity and resilience building activities, and also engaging stakeholders. While accounting for external and regional sociopolitical trends, the risk monitoring practice has been pointed out. By identifying emerging risks early and taking prompt action, organizations are able to protect the project objectives by using all-encompassing risk monitoring methods to remain vigilant (Dafflon & Mariani, 2018).

Somalia is a nation of prolonged conflict, unstable political system, and brittle governance framework. Risks identification practice plays a role in identifying socioeconomic challenges, infrastructure deficiencies, and security risks as the major roadblocks to project's success. With the use of the practice, stakeholders can know and handle possible threats, which ensures project resilience amid difficulties (Samuel & Kumar, 2018). Factors including environmental vulnerabilities, differences in geography and clan, influences the practice of risk assessment. However, completion of risk assessment practice comprehensively, enables stakeholders to strategically allocate resources and prioritize risks to minimize their impact on project outcomes (Abdulle & Ahmed, 2017). Improvement of project resilience and support of sustainable development in Somalia, can be achieved by putting into practice specifically risk mitigation strategies through, community engagement programs, capacity-building initiatives, and resilience-building activities (United Nations Peacekeeping, n.d.). In addition, by implementing strong risk monitoring systems problems can be noted early and proactive steps taken to foster project objectives (World Bank, 2020)

Mogadishu acts as the centre of operations for the ATMIS Project in Somalia, it offers unique chances and challenges for managing project risk. Risk identification technique is critical in the pointing out risks that seriously jeopardize project implementation, political instability, terrorism, and poor infrastructure. The intricacy of risk assessment is exacerbated by elements including urbanization trends, population displacement, and clan dynamics. Risk monitoring is important in Mogadishu to adjust to the dynamic security topography and emerging threats. Stakeholders can keep up with evolving risk dynamics and any disruptions by regularly monitoring and assessing identified risks. (World Bank, 2020).

Globally, the successful execution of projects in various sectors depends on the application of project management practices, efficiently. Unfortunately, current research shows that project management still has challenges, especially in areas where violence has taken precedence and operational complexity has increased. According to the Project Management Institute's 2017 Pulse of the Profession report, inadequate risk management practices, insufficient resources, and stakeholder displacement are just a few of the problems that organizations around the world often face, which eventually cause delays, overspending, and eventually project failure. The major risks that ATMIS project faced were mostly associated with project risk management practices in the context of peacebuilding operations. Operational incompetence, lack of project management techniques knowledge, and resources misuse continued to stabilize the area. Samuel and Kumar (2018), for example, point out the challenges in implementing project risk management in infrastructure projects in areas prone to violence, like Somalia. The challenges are mostly misapplication of project risk management practices; risk identification, risk assessment, risk mitigation and risk monitoring.

The ATMIS Project could have faced consequences if the deficiencies in project risk management were not solved. For stability and peace building objectives to be achieved, operational inefficiencies and resource misuse. (Arowolo, 2019; Puplampu & Akakpo, 2016) however, application of project risk management techniques efficiently, could bring in various definite

effects, like better project outcomes, stakeholder satisfaction, and project resilience. Consequently, the effectiveness and sustainability of peacebuilding programs are intensified by good project riskmanagement techniques, establishing enduring peace and stability in areas ruined by violence.

The African Union Transition Mission Project in Somalia had distinctive opportunities and challenges that were not well realized, despite the significance of project risk management in peacebuilding projects, advancing. Past research has focused more on project management processes in conflict-affected areas or on larger peacekeeping/building programs in Africa. Munene (2016) brings out an analysis of the African Union's peacekeeping attempt in Somalia; however, it does not explicitly deal with project risk management. Nshimiyimana (2020) similarly, looks into project management processes in African UN peacekeeping operations; nevertheless, the ATMIS project was not the main subject of the research. Therefore, the study sought to determine effect of risk identification practice on performance African union transitionmission project in Somalia.

2. RISK IDENTIFICATION

Risk identification is the initial practice in PRM, whereby it focuses on a systematic and thorough search of risks that may likely influence the outcomes of the projects. Across the world, organizations have trouble in identifying risks due to complexity, and any additional unpredicted event (Project Management Institute, 2017). In risk identification there are indicators that are used as techniques in the practice; mind mapping, nominal group technique and brainstorming. Mind mapping is a visual tool that is used to organize information and in this it allows teams to visually explore the relationships between different factors that might contribute to risks. According to Burgess-Allen & Owen-Smith (2010), the use of a mind mapping approach to managing qualitative data can provide a pragmatic resolution of the tension between limited resources and quality in stakeholders participation processes.

The nominal group technique is a structural method for generating and prioritizing ideas, ensuring all participants have equal opportunities in contributing to consensus on which risks are most notable. Bhandari & Hallowell (2021) argues that researchers rely on the collection and analysis of expert opinions as an alternative method, the nominal group technique, is often used to solicit opinions through different processes and controls. Brainstorming is a creative technique used to generate a wide range of ideas, it helps in prospecting as many potential risks as possible, without initially evaluating or analyzing them. This technique involves group discussion to produce ideas and identify risks. It relies on multidisciplinary teams to produce creative ideas (Kobo-Greenhut, Ayala, et al, 2019)

In the case of Somalia, some of the risks include Political risks – due to political instability, Conflict risks – being in an active conflict zone, Infrastructure risks – poor infrastructure. These risks, once identified, are put into account to avoid them or reduce the likelihood of their occurrence in a political climate when management of risks is critical (Samuel and Kumar, 2018).

ATMIS's main goals included stakeholders' satisfaction, capacity building, and economic empowerment. Such objectives were significant in the mission and its sustainability and, when analyzed as variables, they give a comprehensive view of the outcomes of ATMIS endeavor. Stakeholders' satisfaction refers to the standard to which the needs and expectations of stakeholders are met. According to Freeman (2017), the components of this objective are customers, employees, investors and community satisfaction. Capacity building is the process of developing and strengthening the skills, abilities, and resources that organizations and communities require to survive, adapt, and progress. This can be based on categories of individual, organization and community capacity building, UNDP (2017). Economic development involves efforts that pursue to improve the economic well-being for a community through job creation, income growth, infrastructure and sustainable development, world bank (2017).

3. METHOD

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design which allowed qualitative and quantitative research approach used. The target population of this study is comprised of 365 from all categories involved in ATMIS project, Mogadishu area, which forms the unit of analysis of the study. The unit of observation included project departmental heads of both police and military, civilian project managers from contracted organizations and partners of the project. This study used stratified sampling techniques where participants were selected from the different categories of groups, which guaranteed that each stratum was equally represented. The sample size of 131 respondents, from the formula made up of the Project Managers,

head of departments and team leaders, was ideal and tested the objectives of the study effectively. The questionnaires were distributed to different members of focus groups and team leaders/managers of different departments or components. The questionnaires were administered via drop and pick method. Piloting was done to test validity and reliability of the data collection instrument. The data obtained from the survey questions was analyzed using statistical software, Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). Multiple regression and person correlation was used to determine the strength of association between the independent variables and the dependent variable.

4. DISCUSSIONS

The specific objective of the study was to determine the effect of risk identification practice and performance African union transition mission project in Somalia. The respondents were requested to indicate their level of agreement on statements relating to the effect of risk identification practice and performance African union transition mission project in Somalia. A 5 point Likert scale was used where 1 symbolized strongly disagree, 2 symbolized disagree, 3 symbolized neutral, 4 symbolized agree and 5 symbolized strongly agree. The results were as presented in Table 1.

From the results, the respondents agreed that brainstorming method is used and very effective in risk identification. This is supported by a mean of 4.671 (std. dv = 0.943). In addition, as shown by a mean of 4.862 (std. dv = 0.876), the respondents agreed that across the world, organizations have trouble in identifying risks due to complexity, and any additional unpredicted event. Further, the respondents agreed that in risk identification there are indicators that are used as techniques in the practice; mind mapping, nominal group technique and brainstorming. This is shown by a mean of 3.831 (std. dv = 0.944).

The respondents also agreed that the use of a mind mapping approach to managing qualitative data can provide a pragmatic resolution of the tension between limited resources and quality in stakeholder's participation processes. This is shown by a mean of 3.986 (std. dv = 0.935). With a mean of 3.683 (std. dv = 0.854), the respondents agreed that the nominal group technique which is widely applied as a structural method for generating and prioritizing ideas, ensuring all participants have equal opportunities in contributing to consensus on which risk are most notable. Further, the respondents agreed that the nominal group technique which is widely applied as a structural method for generating and prioritizing ideas, ensuring all participants have equal opportunities in contributing to consensus on which risk are most notable. This is shown by a mean of 3.981 (std. dv = 0.746).

Table 1: Risk Identification Practice and Performance African Union Transition Mission Project in Somalia

	Mean	Std. Deviation
Brainstorming method is used and very effective in risk identification	4.671	0.943
Across the world, organizations have trouble in identifying risks due to complexity, and any additional unpredicted event	4.862	0.876
In risk identification there are indicators that are used as techniques in the practice; mind mapping, nominal group technique and brainstorming	3.831	0.944
The use of a mind mapping approach to managing qualitative data can provide a pragmatic resolution of the tension between limited resources and quality in stakeholders participation processes	3.986	0.935
The nominal group technique which is widely applied as a structural method for generating and prioritizing ideas, ensuring all participants have equal opportunities in contributing to consensus on which risk are most notable	3.683	0.854
The use of a mind mapping approach to managing qualitative data provides a pragmatic resolution of the tension between limited resources and quality in stakeholder's participation processes	3.981	0.746
Aggregate	3.982	0.876

4.1. Effect of Performance African Union Transition Mission Project in Somalia

The respondents were requested to indicate their level of agreement on various statements relating to the effect of performance African union transition mission project in Somalia. A 5 point Likert scale was used where 1 symbolized strongly disagree, 2 symbolized disagree, 3 symbolized neutral, 4 symbolized agree and 5 symbolized strongly agree. The results were as presented in table 2.

From the results, the respondents agreed that the ATMIS's main goals should be focused on stakeholders' satisfaction, capacity building, and the economic empowerment. This is supported by a mean of 4.084 (std. dv = 0.997). In addition, as shown by a mean of 3.917 (std. dv = 0.831), the respondents agreed that a suitable risk management practices should assist the management team to achieve high performance in the organization. Further, the respondents agreed that for the successful projects outcome, the stakeholder's needs and expectations should be met. This is shown by a mean of 3.858 (std. dv = 0.563). The respondents also agreed that for a project to be successful, it has to record high returns and identify performance drivers from the top to the bottom of the organization. This is shown by a mean of 3.831 (std. dv = 0.851). With a mean of 3.751 (std. dv = 0.935), the respondents agreed that organizational performance should relate to how successfully an organized group of people with a particular purpose of commitment perform a function to achieve great results measured in terms of the value delivered to customers. The respondent further agreed that capacity building should be focused on the process of developing and strengthening the skills, abilities, and resources that organizations and communities require to survive, adapt, and progress. This is shown by a mean of 3.882 (std. dv = 0.824).

Table 2: Effect of Performance African Union Transition Mission Project in Somalia

	Mean	Std. Deviation
The ATMIS's main goals should be focused on stakeholders' satisfaction, capacity building, and the economic empowerment	4.084	0.997
A suitable risk management practices should assist the management team to achieve high performance in the organization	3.917	0.831
For the successful projects outcome, the stakeholder's needs and expectations should be met	3.858	0.563
For a project to be successful, it has to record high returns and identify performance drivers from the top to the bottom of the organization	3.831	0.851
Organizational performance should relate to how successfully an organized group of people with a particular purpose of commitment perform a function to achieve great results measured in terms of the value delivered to customers	3.751	0.935
Capacity building should be focused on the process of developing and strengthening the skills, abilities, and resources that organizations and communities require to survive, adapt, and progress	3.882	0.824
Aggregate	3.836	0.818

4.2 Inferential Statistics

Inferential statistics in the current study focused on correlation and regression analysis. Correlation analysis was used to determine the strength of the relationship while regression analysis was used to determine the relationship between dependent variable (performance African union transition mission project in Somalia) and independent variables (risk identification practice).

4.2.1 Correlation Analysis

The present study used Pearson correlation analysis to determine the strength of association between independent variables (risk identification practice) and the dependent variable (performance African union transition mission project in Somalia). Pearson correlation coefficient range between zero and one, whereby the strength of association increase with increase in the value of the correlation coefficients. The current study employed Taylor (2018) correlation coefficient ratings whereby 0.80 to 1.00 depicts a very strong relationship, 0.60 to 0.79 depicts strong, 0.40 to 0.59 depicts moderate, 0.20 to 0.39 depicts weak.

Table 4.1: Correlation Coefficients

		Performance African union transition mission project	Risk identification practice
Performance African union transition mission project	Pearson Correlation	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)		
	N	100	
Risk identification practice	Pearson Correlation	.853**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	
	N	100	100

From the results from table 3 above indicates that there was a very strong relationship between risk identification practice and performance African union transition mission project in Somalia ($r = 0.853$, p value = 0.002). The relationship was significant since the p value 0.002 was less than 0.05 (significant level).

4.2.2 Regression Analysis

Multivariate regression analysis was used to assess the relationship between independent variables (risk identification practice) and the dependent variable (performance African union transition mission project in Somalia).

Table 4.4: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.921	.812	.802	.10120

a. Predictors: (Constant), Risk Identification Practice,

The model summary was used to explain the variation in the dependent variable that could be explained by the independent variables. The r -squared for the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable was 0.812. This implied that 81.2% of the variation in the dependent variable (performance African union transition mission project in Somalia) could be explained by independent variables (risk identification practice).

Table 4.5: Analysis of Variance

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	19.022	1	3.231	52.35	.000 ^b
1 Residual	6.518	99	.032		
Total	25.530	100			

a. Dependent Variable: Performance African Union Transition Mission Project in Somalia

b. Predictors: (Constant), Risk Identification Practice,

The ANOVA was used to determine whether the model was a good fit for the data. F calculated was 52.35 while the F critical was 2.412. The p value was 0.000. Since the F -calculated was greater than the F -critical and the p value 0.000 was less than 0.05, the model was considered as a good fit for the data. Therefore, the model can be used to predict the effect of risk identification practice on performance African union transition mission project in Somalia.

Table 4.61: Regression Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	0.406	0.038		4.364	0.000
	Risk identification practice	0.398	0.099	0.397	3.755	0.004

a Dependent Variable: Performance African Union Transition Mission Project In Somalia

The regression model was as follows:

$$Y = 0.406 + 0.398X_1 + \epsilon$$

According to the results, risk identification practice has a significant effect on performance African union transition mission project in Somalia ($\beta_1=0.398$, p value= 0.004). The relationship was considered significant since the p value 0.004 was less than the significant level of 0.05.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the study concluded that risk identification practice has a significant effect on performance African union transition mission project in Somalia ($\beta_1=0.398$, p value= 0.004). The relationship was considered significant since the p value of 0.004, was less than the significant level of 0.05. The study came up with the following recommendations; the management should conduct a thorough risk identification, for indicators that should be used as techniques in the practice; mind mapping, nominal group technique and brainstorming to avoid trouble in identifying risks due to complexity, and any additional unpredicted event and that the use of a mind mapping approach to managing qualitative data can provide a pragmatic resolution of the tension between limited resources and quality in stakeholders participation processes. The African union transition mission project management should continuously do an evaluation of the established risks in relation to risk probability to concentrate their efforts on the most dangerous ones. They should adopt a clear procedure to map risks to better allocate resources to potential consequence of a risk event, helping in understanding the severity of a risk through subjective assessment either major or minor and also financial quantification analysis like cost at benefits or value at risk.

REFERENCES

- [1] Aven, T. (2017). Risk Assessment and Risk Management: *Review of Recent Advances on Their Foundation*. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 253(1), 1-13
- [2] Abdulle, A. H., & Ahmed, S. (2017). An analysis of challenges and opportunities facing therebuilding of the Somali state. *Journal of Public Administration and Governance*, 7(4), 87-104
- [3] Arowolo, D. (2019). Risk management in African Union peace support operations. *African Security Review*, 28(4), 322-334.
- [4] Baldwin, R. E. (2021). *Economic development and export growth: a study of Northern Rhodesia, 1920-1960*. University of California Press.
- [5] Bhandari, S., & Hallowell, M. R. (2021). Identifying and controlling biases in expert-opinion research: *Guidelines for variations of Delphi, nominal group technique, and focus groups*. *Journal of Management in Engineering*, 37(3), 04021015.
- [6] Bonnafous-Boucher, M., & Porcher, S. (2010). Towards a stakeholder society: *Stakeholder theory vs theory of civil society*. *European Management Review*, 7(4), 205-216.
- [7] Bougie, Roger, and Uma Sekaran. *Research methods for business: A skill building approach*. John Wiley & Sons, 2019.
- [8] Bougie, R. and Sekaran, U., 2019. *Research methods for business: A skill building approach*. John Wiley & Sons.
- [9] Burgess-Allen, J., & Owen-Smith, V. (2010). Using mind mapping techniques for rapid qualitative data analysis in public participation processes. *Health Expectations*, 13(4), 406-415.
- [10] Buzan, T. (2024). *Mind map mastery: The complete guide to learning and using the most powerful thinking tool in the universe*. Jaico Publishing House.
- [11] Chapman, R. J. (1998). The effectiveness of working group risk identification and assessment techniques. *International Journal of Project Management*, 16(6), 333-343.
- [12] Chapman, R. J. (2017). *Simple Tools and Techniques for Enterprise Risk Management*. Wiley.
- [13] COSO. (2017). *Enterprise Risk Management: Integrating with Strategy and Performance*. Committee of Sponsoring Organizations of the Treadway Commission.
- [14] Cronbach, L. J. (1951). Coefficient alpha and the internal structure of tests. *Psychometrika*, 16, 297–324. Cronbach, L. J., & Shavelson, J. R. (2004). My current thoughts on coefficient alpha and successor procedures. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 64, 391–418

- [15] Dmytriiev, S. D., Freeman, R. E., & Hörisch, J. (2021). The relationship between stakeholder theory and corporate social responsibility: *Differences, similarities, and implications for social issues in management*. *Journal of Management Studies*, 58(6), 1441-1470.
- [16] Donaldson, T., & Preston, L. E. (1995). The Stakeholder Theory of the Corporation: *Concepts, Evidence, and Implications*. *Academy of Management Review*, 20(1), 65-91.
- [17] Friedman, A. L., & Miles, S. (2002). Developing stakeholder theory. *Journal of management studies*, 39(1), 1-21.
- [18] Freeman, R. E. (2017). *Strategic Management: A Stakeholder Approach*. Cambridge University Press.
- [19] Harrison, J. S., Bosse, D. A., & Phillips, R. A. (2010). Managing for stakeholders, stakeholder utility functions, and competitive advantage. *Strategic management journal*, 31(1), 58-74.
- [20] Hopkin, P. (2017). *Fundamentals of Risk Management: Understanding, Evaluating and Implementing Effective Risk Management*. Kogan Page Publishers.
- [21] ISO 31000:2018. Risk Management - Guidelines. *International Organization for Standardization*.
- [22] Malizia, E., Feser, E. J., Renski, H., & Drucker, J. (2020). Understanding local economic development. *Routledge*.
- [23] Mekonnen, F. (2019). An assessment of risk management practices: *in the case of ethiotelecom tower construction project (Doctoral dissertation, St. Mary's University)*.
- [24] Munene, M. B. (2016). Peacekeeping and peacebuilding: *African Union in Somalia (AMISOM)*.
- [25] Nshimiyimana, J. P. (2020). Project management practices and performance of peacekeeping missions in Africa: *A case of the United Nations Mission in South Sudan*.
- [26] Kothari, C. R., & Garg, G. (2014). *Research methodology: Methods and techniques*. New Delhi: New Age International Publishers.
- [27] Leigh, N. G., & Blakely, E. J. (2016). Planning local economic development: *Theory and practice*. SAGE publications.
- [28] Leech, N. L., Barrett, K. C., & Morgan, G. A. (2014). *IBM SPSS for intermediate statistics: Use and interpretation*. Routledge.
- [29] Mrangu, R. G. (2018). *Assessment of the Factors Affecting Sustainability of Community Based Projects in Rural Areas: A Case of Bagamoyo District, Tanzania (Doctoral dissertation, The Open University of Tanzania)*.
- [30] Mrangu, L. (2022). Rubric as assessment tool for lecturers and students in higher education institution. *Acta Pedagogica Asiana*, 1(1), 26-33.
- [31] Nicola, K., Waugh, J., Charles, E., & Russell, T. (2018). The feasibility and concurrent validity of performing the Movement Assessment Battery for Children—2nd Edition via telerehabilitation technology. *Research in developmental disabilities*, 77, 40-48.
- [32] PMI. (2017). *A Guide to the Project Management Body of Knowledge (PMBOK Guide), 6th Edition*. Project Management Institute.
- [33] Polit, Denise F., and Cheryl Tatano Beck (2006): "The content validity index: are you sure you know what's being reported? Critique and recommendations." *Research in nursing & health* 29, no. 5 (2006): 489-497.
- [34] Puplampu, K. P., & Akakpo, K. K. (2016). Risk management practices in humanitarian projects in Africa: *A study of Ghana and Nigeria*.
- [35] Russell, R., A. D. Guerry, P. Balvanera, R. K. Gould, X. Basurto, K. M. A. Chan, S. Klain, J. Levine and J. Tam (2013). "Humans and nature: How knowing and experiencing nature affect well-being." *Annual Review of Environment and Resources* 38(1): 473-502. [url](#)
- [36] Russell, D. W. 2013. "In Search of Underlying Dimensions: The Use (and Abuse) of Factor Analysis in Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin." *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin* 28: 1629–1646.

- [37] Samuel, J. A., & Kumar, N. (2018). Implementation of project risk management in infrastructure projects in conflict-affected regions: *A case study of Somalia*.
- [38] Suleiman, Yusuf, Bolaji Hameed Olalekan, Ganiyu Mutiu Adegkunle, Mustapha Adam Ishola, and Jimoh Abdulrasheed. "Scale Validity and Reliability of Social Media and Entrepreneurial Skill Development among Tertiary Institution Students in Nigeria." *Journal of Technology Management and Business* 7, no. 1 (2020): 10-24.
- [39] Suleiman, Y., Olalekan, B.H., Adegkunle, G.M., Ishola, M.A. and Abdulrasheed, J., 2020. Scale Validity and Reliability of Social Media and Entrepreneurial Skill Development among Tertiary Institution Students in Nigeria. *Journal of Technology Management and Business*, 7(1), pp.10-24.
- [40] Vogel, M. (2019). Risks and challenges in peacekeeping and peace building: *African Union and United Nations experiences in Darfur*.
- [41] United Nations Peacekeeping. (n.d.). African Union Mission in Somalia (AMISOM). Retrieved from <https://peacekeeping.un.org/en/mission/amisom>
- [42] UNDP. (2017). Capacity Development: *A UNDP Primer. United Nations Development Programme*.
- [43] World Bank. (2017). World Development Report 2017: *Governance and the Law. World Bank Group*.
- [44] Yaghmal, (2003). "Content validity index: A simple but significant approach in social science research." *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal* 8.3 (2018): 36-42.
- [45] Zarefar, A., & Sawarjuwono, T. (2021). Corporate social responsibility: *Theory, practice and its impact on the company. Jurnal Akuntansi Keuangan dan Bisnis*, 14(1), 103-112.